

A Novel Route to the Synthesis of 3-Arylimino-5-Substituted-1,2,4-Dithiazoles. Part I : Oxidative Debenzylation and Cyclisation of S-Benzyliso-N-Arylthiocarbamoyl-Thioacetamides

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Manuscript received 26 September 1977, revised 12 June 1978, accepted 29 October 1980

A novel route to the synthesis of 3-phenylimino-5-methyl-, 3-*p*-Cl-phenylimino-5-methyl-, 3-*p*-tolylimino-5-methyl- and 3-*p*-methoxyphenylimino-5-methyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles, through the oxidative debenzylation and cyclisation of the corresponding S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides, has been described.

ALTHOUGH a number of 3-imino-5-substituted-imino-, 3, 5-disubstitutedimino- and 3-substituted-imino-5-disubstitutedamino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines/dithiazolines have been prepared by various methods¹⁻¹¹, only a few 3-arylimino-5-aryl-1,2,4-dithiazoles (I), obtained by the interaction of thioacetamide and aryliminochloromethane-sulphenylchloride, have been reported¹².

In view of the reported low yields of these 1, 2, 4-dithiazoles and with the object of investigating the possibility of oxidative debenzylation and cyclisation reaction in S-benzylisothiamide system, it was considered worthwhile to search for an alternative route of synthesis for this new class of compounds.

The present communication reports a novel route to the synthesis of 3-arylimino-5-methyl-1, 2, 4-dithiazoles (IV) through the oxidative debenzylation and cyclisation of S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides(III).

Following Werner's procedure¹³, thioacetamide was benzylated with benzylchloride in presence of sodium methoxide. The expected S-benzylisothioacetamide(II) was condensed with appropriate arylisothiocyanate. The reaction afforded the desired S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioaceta-

mides(III), which on oxidation with bromine in chloroform solution, resulted in the formation of a debenzylated and cyclised product, 3-arylimino-5-methyl-1, 2, 4-dithiazoles (IV). The structure of IV was finally settled, as they were also obtained by the direct oxidation of the related N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides (V). V were obtained by the reductive debenzylation of the corresponding S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides(III) with dry hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine solution¹⁴ and also by reduction of the related dithiazole(IV) under identical conditions. Compounds IV and V were characterised by the elemental analysis, mixture melting point technique and identical IR spectra.

The scheme of the reactions can be represented as follows :

where R = phenyl-, *p*-tolyl-, *p*-Cl-phenyl-
or *p*-methoxyphenyl group
Bz = benzyl group.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes. Infrared spectra were recorded in Nujol on a Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer (Model-720).

S-Benzyliso-thioacetamides(II) : Thioacetamide (5 g) was benzylated with benzyl chloride (8.5 ml) in methanol (20 ml) in presence of sodium methoxide (3.75 g). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 hrs and was allowed to stand overnight. It was then refluxed for about 15 minutes. Excess of the solvent was evaporated and the resulting product was extracted with benzene and dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. Evaporation of excess benzene, afforded the desired *S*-benzyliso-thioacetamide(II), which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 48°, (yield 65%).

S-Benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides(III) : The details of a typical experiment are as follows :

S-Benzylisothioacetamide(II) (5 g) was refluxed with phenylisothiocyanate (4.2 ml) and 15 ml of sodium hydroxide (10%) for 30 minutes. The semi-solid product was extracted with benzene and the extract further refluxed for 30 minutes. The resulting mass obtained, on evaporation of the solvent, was washed with petroleum ether (40–60°) and then treated with ethanol to afford the expected *S*-benzyliso-*N*-phenylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide(III) which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 128°, (yield 72%).

These results are summarised in Table 1.

3-Arylimino-5-methyl-1, 2, 4-dithiazoles(IV) :

(i) *Oxidative debenzylation and cyclisation of S*-benzyliso-*N*-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides(III) : Details of a representative experiment are as

 TABLE 1—*S*-BENZYLISO-*N*-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-THIOACETAMIDES

Reactants	S-benzyliso- <i>N</i> -arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides formed	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
Phenylisothiocyanate+SBT	S-benzyliso- <i>N</i> -phenylthiocarbamoyl-T	72	128	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ S ₂	N : 9.07 S : 22.04	9.33 21.33
<i>p</i> -Cl-phenylisothiocyanate+SBT	S-benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Cl-phenylthiocarbamoyl-T	69	140	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	N : 8.54 S : 20.40	8.97 19.14
<i>p</i> -tolylisothiocyanate+SBT	S-benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -tolylthiocarbamoyl-T	65	145	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂	C : 65.38 H : 5.79 N : 8.81	64.96 6.73 8.91
<i>p</i> -methoxyphenylisothiocyanate+SBT	S-benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -methoxyphenylthiocarbamoyl-T	63	195	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ S ₂ O	N : 8.62 S : 19.50	8.48 19.39

SBT—denotes *S*-benzylisothioacetamide,
T—denotes thioacetamide.

Characteristic IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) of *S*-Benzyliso-*N*-phenylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide : 3210m, NH stretching (Lit^{1*} 3400-3100), 1160m, 1170w, 1195w, N-C(=S)-N grouping (Lit^{1*} 1200-1600).

 TABLE 2—3-ARYLIMINO-5-METHYL-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLES : OXIDATIVE DEBENZYLATION AND CYCLISATION OF *S*-BENZYLISO-*N*-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-THIOACETAMIDES

S-Benzyliso- <i>N</i> -arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide oxidised	3-Arylimino-5-methyl-1,2,4-dithiazole formed	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
S-Benzyliso- <i>N</i> -phenyl-TT	3-phenylimino-5-methyl-DT	65	158	C ₉ H ₈ N ₂ S ₂	N : 13.28 S : 31.08	13.46 30.76
S-benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-TT	3- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenylimino-5-methyl-DT	60	194	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	C : 45.30 H : 3.01 N : 11.70	44.53 2.88 11.54
S-benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -tolyl-TT	3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-5-methyl-DT	68	162	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂	S : 26.20 C : 53.84 H : 4.20	26.39 54.05 4.50
S-benzyliso- <i>N</i> - <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-TT	3- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenylimino-5-methyl-DT	63	145	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ O	N : 12.84 S : 29.12	12.61 29.00
					N : 12.08 S : 26.66	11.77 26.89

TT—denotes thiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide,
DT—denotes 1,2,4-dithiazole,

Characteristic IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 3-phenylimino-5-methyl-1,2,4-dithiazole : Ring -C-S (1070m)^{1*}, C=N (1620s)^{1*}, ring -S-S-linkage (490m)^{1*}.

TABLE 3—3-ARYLIMINO-5-METHYL-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLES: OXIDATION OF N-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-THIOACETAMIDES WITH BROMINE IN DILUTE ETHANOL

N-Arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide oxidised	3-Arylimino-5-methyl-1,2,4-dithiazole formed	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
N-phenylthiocarbamoyl-T	3-phenylimino-5-methyl-DT	70	157	C ₉ H ₈ N ₂ S ₂	N : 13.23 S : 30.48	13.46 30.76
N-p-Cl-phenylthiocarbamoyl-T	3-p-Cl-phenylimino-5-methyl-DT	65	194	C ₉ H ₇ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	N : 10.98 S : 27.01	11.54 26.39
N-p-tolylthiocarbamoyl-T	3-p-tolylimino-5-methyl-DT	75	163-64	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂	C : 54.78 H : 4.98	54.05 4.50
N-p-methoxyphenylthiocarbamoyl-T	3-p-methoxyphenylimino-5-methyl-DT	73	145	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂ O	N : 12.42 N : 12.25 S : 26.58	12.61 11.77 26.89

T—denotes thioacetamide,
DT—denotes 1,2,4-dithiazole.

TABLE 4—N-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-THIOACETAMIDES: REDUCTIVE DEBENZYLATION OF S-BENZYLISO-N-ARYLTHIOCARBAMOYL-THIOACETAMIDES WITH HYDROGEN SULPHIDE IN PYRIDINE-TRIETHYLAMINE MEDIUM

S-Benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide reduced	N-Arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide formed	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	Analysis	
					Found	Reqd.
S-benzyliso-N-phenyl-TT	N-phenylthiocarbomoyl-T	82	148	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂	C : 52.08 H : 4.79 N : 14.03	51.42 4.76 13.33
S-benzyliso-N-p-Cl-phenyl-TT	N-p-Cl-phenylthiocarbomoyl-T	78	160	C ₉ H ₉ N ₂ S ₂ Cl	N : 10.96 S : 26.52	11.45 26.17
S-benzyliso-N-p-tolyl-TT	N-p-tolylthiocarbomoyl-T	85	152	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂	N : 11.71 S : 29.12	12.50 28.57
S-benzyliso-N-p-methoxyphenyl-TT	N-p-methoxyphenylthiocarbomoyl-T	79	187	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂ O	C : 49.58 H : 4.85 S : 27.58	50.00 5.08 26.66

TT—denotes thiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide,
T—denotes thioacetamide.

Characteristic IR frequencies (cm⁻¹) of N-phenylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide: 3220m, NH stretching (Lit¹⁵ 3400-3100), 1170m, N-C(=S)-N grouping (Lit¹⁵ 1200-1600), 1370, C=S grouping (Lit¹⁷ 1400-1100).

follows :

To a paste of S-benzyliso-N-phenylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide (5 g) in chloroform (2 ml), was added bromine (1 ml) in small portions with vigorous stirring. Debonylation was evident from the evolution of the lachrymatory fumes of benzyl bromide. After allowing the reaction mixture to stand for 30 minutes, it was washed with ether. Treatment of the residue with ethanol afforded the desired 3-phenylimino-5-methyl-1, 2, 4-dithiazole hydrobromide, which on basification with ammonia resulted in the free base (IV), which was crystallised from ethanol, m.p, 158°, (yield 65%). These results are presented in Table 2.

(ii) *Oxidation of N-Arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides(V) with bromine in dilute ethanol* : The substituted-thioacetamides (5 g) (V) listed in Table 4 were oxidised with bromine (0.7 ml) in dilute ethanol solution. On addition of ether, the hydrobromides of the respective 1,2,4-dithiazoles(IV) got precipitated. Free bases were obtained by treating

these with ammonia which were then crystallised from ethanol. These were found to be identical with the respective 3-arylimino-5-methyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles recorded in Table 2. The identity was confirmed from undepressed mixture melting points and superimposable IR spectra.

The results are given in Table 3.

N-Arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides(V) :

(a) *Reductive debonylation of S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamides(III)* : The appropriate S-benzyliso-N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide (III) was dissolved in a mixture of pyridine and triethylamine (1 : 6) and a stream of dry hydrogen sulphide passed for 3 hrs. The reaction mixture on pouring over crushed ice and acidification with hydrochloric acid afforded the related N-arylthiocarbamoyl-thioacetamide(V), which was filtered out and crystallised from ethanol. The results are recorded in Table 4.

(b) *Reduction of 3-arylimino-5-methyl-1,2,4-dithiazoles(IV) with hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine medium*: The related 1,2,4-dithiazoles(IV) were reduced in pyridine-triethylamine medium by passing dry hydrogen sulphide gas for about 2 hrs. On dilution with water and acidification of the resulting solution, the expected N-arylthiocarbonyl-thioacetamide(V) was obtained. These were crystallised from ethanol.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the Professor-in-charge, Applied Chemistry Section, Institute of Technology and the Head, Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University for the facilities and one of us (R.R.) also expresses his gratitude to the University Grants Commission for a Junior Research Fellowship.

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